

**Combating gender stereotypes by
highlighting women's contribution to the
history of societies**

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1. Gender equality and gender representation in Lithuania

The history of Lithuanian society and statehood is quite reflective of one of the central issues concerning gender equality, namely, the challenge of turning the vision or a set of ideas into a tangible social change and bringing equality into the everyday lives of people. The first establishment of the Lithuanian Republic in 1918, period of an autocratic regime, following occupations by an ideology driven USSR, reestablishment of independence in the 1990s and a huge political transformation leading to the EU membership has made Lithuanian society face a diverse range of political visions and sets of values being promoted and often imposed on the society sometimes in a complete disregard of the social reality. Therefore, a degree of disparity between what is the officially promoted vision of the society (including the gender equality aspect) and the way how society functions in reality is perceived as natural, at least by the local population. Supporting an idea regardless of whether to survive in an oppressive regime or to join the EU does not necessarily translate into change of the social norms which are being enforced daily and remain out of control of the government officials.

This point is important given the context of official policies and legal frameworks related to gender equality and pursued by different governments over time. During the period of Soviet occupation, equality between men and women was claimed in economic and social life with specific emphasis on employment. However, this was not a matter of choice given the “full employment” policy in the USSR as well as the necessity for both partners in the family to work due to low salaries. At the same, gender stereotypes and patriarchal views remained unchallenged or reinforced as in other Central and Eastern European countries.¹

Following the restoration of independence, a lot of work had to be accomplished to establish formal institutional and legal frameworks to tackle gender inequality. Namely, an Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson was established, laws on Equal Treatment and on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men passed as well as a number of international conventions ratified, and EU Directives implemented. Nevertheless, in the most recent Gender Equality index Lithuania scored 60 points out of 100 and ranked 20th in the EU on the Gender Equality

¹ Gruzevskis, B., Kanopiene, V. (2016). Lithuania. In Razzu, G. (Ed.). (2016). *Gender Inequality in the Eastern European Labour Market: Twenty-five years of transition since the fall of communism*. (1st ed., pp. 152) Taylor & Francis.

Index.2 Even with the 53 % of the population being female3 Lithuania is still facing significant obstacles to gender equality mostly related to structural constraints which limit the effects of the mentioned laws and regulations.

1.1. Gender segregation in the labour market

One of the most apparent and long-existing structural constraints related to gender equality is gender segregation in the labour market. Certain sectors in Lithuania are historically dominated by male or female gender resulting in existence of “masculine” and “feminine” sectors, choice of which prospective labour force makes even before the employment process – when starting the vocational training.⁴ In 2022, more than 80 % of workers were male in construction and transportation sectors, at the same time more than 80 % of workers were female in the health care and social work sector, more than 78 % – in education and more than 73 % – in accommodation and restaurant services.⁵ The trend remains largely unchanged since the restoration of independence. In addition to a clear horizontal gender segregation Lithuania is also facing a vertical segregation due to less women occupying leadership positions.

1.2. Gender pay-gap

The segregation in the labour market also translates into wages which reinforce gender inequality even further. The gender pay gap in Lithuania in 2022 was 11.1 % and remained unchanged in comparison with 2021. The largest gender pay gaps were recorded in enterprises engaged in financial and insurance activities – 31.8 %, information and communication – 28.4 %, health care and social work activities – 25.6 %. In enterprises engaged in transportation and storage and construction activities, average gross hourly earnings of women exceeded that of men therefore the gap was negative and stood at –11.9 % and – 3.6 % respectively.⁶

² European Institute for Gender Equality. *Gender Equality Index*. Retrieved from: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2022/country/LT#:~:text=Best%20performance,which%20it%20scores%2073.9%20points>.

³ The World Bank Data. *Population, female (% of total population) - Lithuania*. Retrieved from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL.FE.ZS?locations=LT>

⁴ Gruzevskis, B., Kanopiene, V. (2016). Lithuania. In Razzu, G. (Ed.). (2016). *Gender Inequality in the Eastern European Labour Market: Twenty-five years of transition since the fall of communism*. (1st ed., pp. 157) Taylor & Francis.

⁵ Official Statistics Portal of Lithuania. *Average number of full- and part-time employees by economic activity*. Retrieved from: <https://osp.stat.gov.lt/en/statistiniu-rodikliu-analize?hash=d2673fd2-18e8-484f-a4e4-9ee382a079e7>

⁶ Official Statistics Portal of Lithuania. *Gender pay gap*. Retrieved from: <https://osp.stat.gov.lt/informaciniai-pranesimai?articleId=11072310>

1.3. Reconciliation of family and work

In addition to the labour market outcomes, a major constraint in Lithuania for gender equality is insufficient reconciliation of family and work. In the 90s, there was an acute shortage of childcare facilities⁷ which limited the possibilities of mothers during that period to pursue careers and consequently still has an effect on their occupations, income and status today. Qualitative study carried out in 2020 showed that availability of pre-school childcare facilities is still one of the biggest concerns for parents.⁸ Other challenges indicated by the respondents include feminised discourses on childcare and lack of information for fathers, stereotypes and cultural norms, unfavourable work environment for taking parental leave, inadequate regulation of parental leave and related benefits, all of which make fathers less likely to take parental leave and putting more family responsibilities on women.⁹ Analysis of the existing Lithuanian legal framework also showed asymmetry in parental rights and benefits which favoured children younger than 14 years old, families with at least 2 children and mothers over fathers.¹⁰

1.4. Gender stereotypes

The most serious structural constraint having impact on the previously mentioned constraints too is gender stereotypes which exist in all possible spheres and affect decisions in everyday life. These stereotypes can not only affect how people treat members of other gender, but also individual decisions taken independently, such as choice of a job or education, as mentioned in the gender segregation section. Men and women in Lithuania are still mostly seen as two groups performing specific roles and functions as well as having distinct features and qualities unrelated to biological differences between sexes. According to a study carried out in 2021, when it comes to statements related to gender stereotypes, approximately one third usually supports them: statement that women should always strive to be attractive was supported by 28 %, a woman must stay at home – by 27 %, men are better drivers than women

⁷ Gruzevskis, B., Kanopiene, V. (2016). Lithuania. In Razzu, G. (Ed.). (2016). *Gender Inequality in the Eastern European Labour Market: Twenty-five years of transition since the fall of communism*. (1st ed., pp. 163) Taylor & Francis.

⁸ Pilinkaitė-Sotirovič, V., Kontvainė, V. (2020). *Šiuolaikiniai vyrai ir lyčių lygybė: paskatos ir kliūtys vyrams įsitraukti į vaiko priežiūrą*. Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson. p. 31.

⁹ Pilinkaitė-Sotirovič, V., Kontvainė, V. (2020). *Šiuolaikiniai vyrai ir lyčių lygybė: paskatos ir kliūtys vyrams įsitraukti į vaiko priežiūrą*. Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson. pp. 31-32.

¹⁰ Vanagelienė, R., Vengalė-Dits, L. (2021). *Lietuvos Respublikos teisės aktų asmeninio gyvenimo ir darbo derinimo klausimais apžvalga*. Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson.

– by 23 %, men should be the main providers for the family – by 21 % of the respondents.¹¹ However, there is a positive dynamic, all of these statements were supported less than in 2019.

2. Gender representation in history in Lithuania

Lithuanian history, as in many other countries, predominantly focuses on male figures such as kings, dukes, military leaders, prominent politicians and writers. Even though there are several well-known female figures among nobility (e.g., Queen Morta, Ona Vytautienė, Bona Sforca, Emilija Pliaterytė), writers and publicists (e.g., Gabrielė Petkevičaitė-Bitė, Julija Beniuševičiūtė-Žymantienė), prominent scientists (e.g., Marija Gimbutienė), women are underrepresented and less talked about even when their importance to Lithuanian history is undisputed. Representation of women is usually based on specific and more prominent individuals and does not provide much information on the life of women in general. Analysis of the linguistic gender representation in English and Lithuanian textbooks on history confirmed that men are represented more frequently, and gender representation is imbalanced. Men are introduced as rulers, decision makers, politicians, etc. and described in similar ways: harsh, powerful, ruthless, persuasive, etc.¹²

3. Gender representation in history in Vilnius

History of Vilnius faces similar issues with gender representation as history of Lithuania. Even though there are famous female historical figures in Lithuanian capital, there is lack of publications and systemic approach focused on the role of women in the history of the city. The topic of the situation of women in Lithuanian cities used to be unexplored until recently.¹³ It is, however, attracting more attention and there is an increasing interest in the topic both among academia and general public, specifically in the form of guided tours about the famous women of Vilnius. Some of the most recent publications about prominent women includes

¹¹ Lithuanian Ministry of Social Security and Labour. (2021). *Report on the sociological survey on the situation of women and men disparities between women and men in Lithuania*. pp.83. Retrieved from: [https://socmin.lrv.lt/uploads/socmin/documents/files/Projektu-konkursai/MVLG%20konkursai/Ataskaita%20-%20SADM%20Moter%C5%B3%20ir%20vyr%C5%B3%20pad%C4%97ties%20skirtumai%20LT%202021%20\(galutin%C4%97\).pdf](https://socmin.lrv.lt/uploads/socmin/documents/files/Projektu-konkursai/MVLG%20konkursai/Ataskaita%20-%20SADM%20Moter%C5%B3%20ir%20vyr%C5%B3%20pad%C4%97ties%20skirtumai%20LT%202021%20(galutin%C4%97).pdf)

¹² Daržinkevič, I. (2020). *Linguistic gender representation in textbooks: a comparative study of textbooks in English and Lithuanian*. Doctoral dissertation., Vytautas Magnus University., pp.35.

¹³ Karpavičienė, J. (2001). *Moteris teisinėje Vilniaus ir Kauno kasdienoje XVI a. pirmojoje pusėje: modernėjančio gyvenimo ženklai. Lietuvos istorijos studijos*, 9, pp. 18

Lithuanian visionaries (Gasiulytė, E., 2020), Women who built Lithuania (Auškalnytė A., 2020), Evening stories for Lithuanian girls - 100 stories about Lithuanian women (Aprimaitė V., Uronaitė V., 2020), Women in the twists and turns of history: rulers, artists, scientists, mystics, heroines, who shaped the history of the city and the world (Baškienė R., 2022). In 2022, Lithuanian National Radio and Television also launched a project *Didmoterės* to commemorate women's role in Lithuanian history by publishing dedicated articles on the portal.¹⁴

4. Female footprint in Vilnius

There are 2971 streets in Vilnius city, 42 out of them have forenames and surnames of honourable women or the names of female historic figures.¹⁵ There are 715 commemorative plaques, sculptures, monuments and other artistic objects installed in Vilnius city. 377 out of them are installed in memory of famous persons (some of them have a few commemorative objects in different places of the city). 22 commemorative plaques, sculptures and monuments are devoted to famous women (writers, artists, scientists, saviour of Jews, participants of resistance, grand duchess, etc.).

The following chapters briefly describe ten women who left footprint in the history of Vilnius city, who were famous not only in Lithuania, also worldwide. All of them were active in the 20th century. Their memory is commemorated in various places of Vilnius city by the name of the streets, monuments, sculptures, and/or commemorative plaques.

4.1. Marija Alseikaitė-Gimbutienė (1921-1994)

Lithuanian archaeologist, pioneer of archaeomythology of the 20th century. She cooperated in various archaeological publications and encyclopedias, participated in scientific conferences, wrote and published books on archaeology and archaeomythology. She mainly studied post-Paleolithic Europe. A long-time lecturer, Professor.¹⁶

¹⁴ Lithuanian National Radio and Television (2022). *DIDMOTERĖS - a new project about prominent Lithuanian women on LRT.lt*. Retrieved from: <https://www.lrt.lt/naujienos/tavo-lrt/15/1749282/didmoterės-naujas-projektas-apie-iskilias-lietuvos-moteris-portale-lrt-lt>

¹⁵ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/streets>

¹⁶ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/persons/C12D2744-7EF5-40DA-B2EF-3742B05BA575>

4.2. Marija Horodničienė (1904-1975)

Lithuanian ophthalmologist of the 20th century. She has done a lot in the field of treatment and prevention of blindness. A long-time lecturer at Vilnius University. In 1999 she received the Life Saviour's Cross Award.

4.3. Jurga Ivanauskaitė (1961-2007)

Lithuanian writer, artist of the 20th – 21st centuries. She wrote a lot of novellas, novels, non-fiction books. Also wrote poems, essays, books for children, illustrated books. Wrote articles on Tibetan freedom, religions, feminism, politics and other thematic.¹⁷

4.4. Marcelė Kubiliūtė (1898-1963)

Lithuanian public figure, active in press, education and military areas. She is the only Lithuanian woman awarded all major Lithuanian orders.¹⁸

4.5. Aldona Liobytė-Paškevičianė (1915-1985)

Children's writer and translator from Vilnius. Her fairy tales, plays, and translations gave Lithuanian children the opportunity to discover both Lithuanian folk wisdom and classics of children's literature from around the world. This was the essence of her resistance to the Soviet occupation: in her works and translations Liobytė helped children to develop into smart, independent, and critically thinking adults.¹⁹

4.6. Meilė Lukšienė (1913-2009)

Literature researcher, pedagogue, educology expert. She was a member of the Lithuanian Reorganization Movement "Sąjūdis" initiative group, and a pioneer of the Lithuanian educational reform, both nationally and internationally.²⁰

4.7. Ieva Simonaitytė (1897-1978)

Writer; an author of autobiographic tales and novels, she depicted everyday life and exceptional destinies of "lietuvninkai" – Lithuanians from Lithuania Minor. She received critical acclaim for her novel Aukštųjų Šimonių likimas (The Fate of Šimoniai from Aukštieji, 1935).²¹

¹⁷ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/persons/6DC81B50-4E3B-4D7D-A0A6-EB6760A59BF2>

¹⁸ Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marcel%C4%97_Kubili%C5%ABt%C4%97

¹⁹ Retrieved from: <https://mokomesapie.lt/en/100/aldona-liobyte-classic-childrens-literature-and-the-resistance-can-fairy-tales-destroy-the-regime/>

²⁰ Retrieved from: https://ml100.ugdome.lt/?page_id=69

²¹ Retrieved from: <http://antologija.lt/author/ieva-simonaityte?lang=en>

4.8. Šatrijos Ragana (1877-1930)

Šatrijos Ragana, the pen name of Marija Pečkauskaitė, a Lithuanian humanist and romantic writer and educator. Pečkauskaitė was one of the first Lithuanian writers to create deep and complex characters, analyzing not only their psychology but also spirituality. She also participated in the First Congress of Lithuanian Women and was elected its vice-chair.²²

4.9. Ona Šimaitė (1894-1970)

Librarian at Vilnius University; used her position to aid and rescue Jews in Vilnius ghetto. Entering the ghetto under the pretext of recovering library books from Jewish university students, she smuggled in food and other provisions and smuggled out literary and historical documents. In 1944, the Nazis arrested and tortured Šimaitė. She was then deported to Dachau and later transferred to a concentration camp in southern France. After the camp was liberated by the Allies, Šimaitė remained in France, working as a librarian, except for a period from 1953 to 1956 spent in Israel. On 15 March 1966, the Israeli organisation Yad Vashem recognized Šimaitė as a Righteous Among the Nations, planting a tree in her honour. Šimaitė died outside of Paris in 1970 and, per her request, her body was donated to science.²³

4.10. Eugenija Šimkūnaitė (1920-1996)

Lithuanian pharmacist, herbalist, ethnographer, Habilitated Doctor of Biomedicine and Biology sciences of the 20th century. She was engaged in pharmacological activities, worked at the Institute of Biology, the Pharmaceutical Board of the Ministry of Health. Researched the habitats of medicinal plants, collected folklore, organised student herb gathering contests. Wrote books on medicinal plants, published scientific and science popularisation articles in various magazines.²⁴

5. Vilnius city's practices in disseminating gender balanced history

Information on practises in disseminating gender balanced history in Vilnius is fragmented due to the large autonomy of Lithuanian municipal administrations and other entities in carrying out educational and/or cultural initiatives. Public institutions set up by the municipal

²² Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/%C5%A0atrijos_Ragana

²³ Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ona_%C5%A0imait%C4%97

²⁴ Retrieved from: <https://zemelapiai.vplanas.lt/vilniausdnr/en/persons/F560B367-4A2C-4120-A74D-2DCFD9E18A1D>

administrations (such as public schools, libraries, museums, cultural centres, etc.) may independently pursue local small-scale initiatives to promote gender balanced history, for example, organise exhibitions, public lectures, tours, and other activities. This is also supported by private efforts and initiatives.

Recently there are a notable increase of exhibitions devoted to famous women, their work and input into the Lithuanian history. For instance, an exhibition for Lithuanian born artist Aleksandra Kasuba or special exhibition “Women warriors”²⁵ telling the stories of women warriors of the 19th and 20th centuries. In addition, guided tours about prominent women who lived in Vilnius are becoming increasingly popular.²⁶ Among many European capitals Vilnius stands out as the city celebrating national Emancipation Day. Each year, on 17 February, right after the celebration of the national Independence Day on the 16th, an alternative highly symbolic celebration is organised commemorating a rally held in Kaunas on this day in 1918 to protest against the exclusion of women among the signatories of Lithuanian independence.²⁷

6. Local strategies

There is no publicly available information on local strategies of promoting gender balanced history. Topics of “gender” or “women” are absent from national history curriculum for the high-school students. These topics are also absent in municipal strategic action plans and strategic development plans.

7. Focus Groups with Young People: Analyses and results

The schoolchildren who participated in the focus group (FG) openly shared that they do not have any particular interest in the field of history. They view it as just one of many compulsory subjects they must take at school, with little personal engagement or enthusiasm. Among all the participants, only one student clearly indicated that history lessons hold any relevance to him. This was not due to a genuine interest in the subject matter itself, but rather because he

²⁵ Retrieved from: <https://lnm.lt/renginiai/kovojusiu-moteru-istorijos-parodoje-kovotojos-xix-xx/>

²⁶ According to Gasiulytė, E. (2018). *History's forgotten Vilnius women would now be Instagram stars*. Retrieved from: <https://madeinvilnius.lt/vilniaus-istorija/vilniaus-miesto-studija/istorijos-pamirstos-vilniaus-moterys-dabar-butu-instagram-zvaigzdemis/>

²⁷ Lithuanian National Radio and Television. (2022). 17 February is National Emancipation Day: Manifesto read in Vilnius, calling for ratification of the Istanbul Convention. Retrieved from: <https://www.lrt.lt/mediateka/irasas/2000201449/vasario-17-oji-nacionaline-emancipacijos-diena-vilniuje-skaitytas-manifestas-raginta-ratifikuoti-stambulo-konvencija>

needs to pass a history exam as a requirement for his intended university studies. This lack of interest among the majority suggests that history, as it is currently taught, fails to capture the attention or imagination of most students. It might be explained by several factors. Firstly, the education programs and teaching methods currently applied in schools may not be designed to make the subject engaging or relevant to students' lives. Traditional approaches to teaching history often rely heavily on memorization of dates and events, which can seem tedious and disconnected from the present. Secondly, teachers themselves may struggle to engage students in a way that sparks curiosity and enthusiasm. If teachers are unable to convey the importance and excitement of historical study, students are less likely to develop a genuine interest in the subject. Moreover, students show a much greater interest in contemporary history and the history of their own country, than of the wider world and other countrys. Research participants also shared that the contributions of women to history are scarcely discussed during history lessons. While they acknowledged that there had been some lessons specifically targeted at this topic, these instances were few and far between. Moreover, only a small number of participants were able to identify notable women from Lithuania's history. Instead, most of the individuals they could name were famous international figures rather than significant female historical figures from their own country.

This lack of focus on women in Lithuanian history suggests a broader issue within the curriculum, where the achievements and impact of women are not sufficiently highlighted. As a result, students are not being exposed to the rich and diverse contributions of Lithuanian women throughout history.

The participants discussed the lack of women representation in Lithuanian history, attributing it to the country's historical context and entrenched patriarchal patterns. They noted that history has traditionally been written from a male-dominated perspective, marginalizing women's contributions. Also members of the TG emphasized the need to reevaluate and include women's significant roles to provide a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of Lithuania's past, promoting gender equality in historical representation. Students mentioned that topics related to gender equality, social inequalities, human rights, and similar issues are rarely addressed in their curriculum. They observed that these

important subjects are often overlooked or given minimal attention. Several reasons were cited for this omission.

One reason identified is the lack of teachers' competencies in these areas. Many educators may not have received adequate training or resources to effectively teach and facilitate discussions on gender equality and human rights. This gap in knowledge and skills can lead to discomfort or avoidance of these topics in the classroom.

Additionally, students pointed out that there is fear among teachers regarding the potential for different opinions on these topics to cause conflicts among students. Given the diverse perspectives that pupils may hold, particularly on issues related to gender and human rights, teachers might be concerned about managing heated debates or disagreements that could arise.

Participants of the focus group shared their opinion about the methods that could be applied to promote knowledge on women's footprint in history and to increase interest of young people in the topic:

- Apply innovative and interactive methods, including orientation games, quiz games, watching movies, initiating discussions, organising lessons outside the school, meeting people who can share their memories of the events of the past, etc.
- Provide information on the specific topic through the lens of young person, for instance, taking examples of the youth 'heroes' and relate them to the historic figures.
- Information provided on particular topic should be made concentrated with more visuals and less text.
- Interactive map could include tasks and clues that need to be solved to reach the next point of the map. It would be also motivating to get some reward after solving all clues and reaching the final point.
- One of the proposals was to combine different subjects to understand the topic deeper, e.g., history and geography, history and maths, etc.

8. Focus Groups with Stakeholders: Analyses and results

In both the focus group discussions and individual interviews, participants highlighted the numerous challenges associated with creating content that focuses on women's contributions to history. These challenges can be broadly categorized as follows:

- a) **Lack of historiography:** Participants noted the scarcity of historical research and documentation specifically dedicated to women's experiences and achievements. This shortage of source material presents a significant obstacle to accurately portraying women's roles in history.
- b) **Lack of methodological material for teachers:** Educators often lack sufficient resources and guidance to effectively incorporate women's history into their teaching methods. Without appropriate methodologies and teaching materials, it becomes challenging for teachers to integrate this content into their curricula in a meaningful way.
- c) **Stereotypical view of history as a male-dominated subject:** There exists a pervasive stereotype that history primarily focuses on the deeds and accomplishments of men, contributing to the marginalization of women's contributions. This narrow perspective of history perpetuates gender biases and inhibits the recognition of women's historical significance.
- d) **Difficulties in attracting a diverse audience:** Content related to women's history is often perceived as relevant only to women, leading to challenges in engaging a broader and more diverse audience. Moreover, there is a particular struggle in capturing the interest of young men, who may not see themselves reflected in narratives centered on women's experiences.
- e) **Lack of commemoration of women in public spaces:** Participants noted the absence of public recognition and commemoration of women who have made significant contributions to history. The lack of statues, monuments, and other forms of public acknowledgment perpetuates the erasure of women's achievements from collective memory and public discourse.

These challenges show that society needs to work together to fill in the gaps in how history represents women. It should be made sure that women's contributions are more visible. If these problems are overcome, it would be possible to have a history that includes everyone's experiences and achievements, no matter their gender.

Research participants also indicated that due to stereotypical attitudes and still existing resistance to the questions related to the feminist tradition it is a challenge to draw attention to such topic as women's footprint in history. As one of the experts shared that people working in this field still have to prove why this topic is important to be taken into account and to find ways to make the topic visible and heard.

One significant reason for the lack of women's representation in the field of history is the prevailing narrative of masculinity, which became particularly entrenched during the Soviet era. During this period, historical content primarily focused on two main themes: the working class, often portrayed in a gender-neutral manner, and male figures depicted as heroes and warriors. Consequently, women's stories and contributions were largely overlooked, resulting in their virtual disappearance from Lithuanian history for a considerable period.

The emphasis on male-centric narratives reinforced traditional gender roles and obscured the roles and achievements of women throughout history. This longstanding focus on masculine ideals perpetuated the marginalization of women's voices and obscured their significant contributions to various aspects of society. As a result, the historical record presented a skewed perspective that failed to accurately reflect the diverse experiences and contributions of women in shaping Lithuanian history.

The research participants noted that more visible changes related to women representation were noticed about five years ago, when first books about women who left their footprint in Lithuania's history were published and the first guiding tours about important female personalities who used to live in Vilnius city were organised. Furthermore, recently the number of the exhibitions devoted for women who left footprint in history increased in Vilnius city. For instance, exhibitions for famous Lithuanian archaeologist and anthropologist Marija Gimbutiene (Gimbutas) and Lithuanian-born artist Aleksandra Kasuba, special exhibition on "Women warriors" telling the stories of women warriors of the 19th and 20th centuries, and others. However, the research participants shared that they still miss representation of women as independent and heroic figures. The representation of women as a 'passive' figure (as someone's wife, daughter, mother, etc.) is still more widespread. Furthermore, the experts emphasised despite the visible changes on women representation, the education system on this subject has been changing at its slowest pace.

Research participants agreed that the teaching methods currently employed in schools to deliver history lessons are outdated and fail to resonate with the younger generation. Despite the natural curiosity and eagerness of today's youth to learn, it is crucial to adopt approaches that effectively engage them. Experts offered valuable insights into potential methods that could capture the interest of young people, not only in the topic of women's contributions to history but also in the subject of history in general:

a) Implement interactive and innovative methods: using various games and digital technologies can make history lessons more engaging and interactive for students. By incorporating interactive elements into the curriculum, educators can create a dynamic learning environment that appeals to the digital-savvy younger generation.

b) Talk about the historical facts through the eyes of young person: By framing historical events and narratives through the eyes of young individuals and providing examples that resonate with their experiences, educators can make history more relatable and emotionally impactful for students. This approach helps students connect with the subject matter on a personal level, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for history.

c) Organizing activities outside of the school: Offering activities outside the traditional classroom setting, such as watching targeted movies and performances, visiting installations and exhibitions, or participating in guided tours, can provide students with hands-on experiences that bring history to life. These immersive activities not only supplement classroom learning but also offer students opportunities to explore history in a more interactive and engaging manner.

By implementing these innovative approaches, educators can make history lessons more relevant, interactive, and appealing to today's youth, thereby fostering a deeper interest and appreciation for both the topic of women's contributions to history and the study of history in general.

The research participants emphasised that while creating the content on female footprint in history, it should be considered women representation equal to men representation also emphasising their cooperation and common participation in certain historical events. The aim should be to show a comprehensive picture of the chosen historic event or certain time of history. Furthermore, the content of women footprint in history should be interesting both for

girls and boys. It should be emphasized that there is a history of humankind and both women and men put a contribution to it and developed it cooperating. It would be a great success if boys also found emotional relation to the told stories on women's footprint in history.

Conclusions

The history of Lithuania has a huge impact on perception of gender equality and how it is applied in practice. Despite the positive changes that were brought after the reestablishment of independence in 1990 and after the joining the EU in 2004, Lithuania is still facing significant obstacles to gender equality mostly related to gender segregation in the labour market, gender pay gap, reconciliation of family and work, as well as gender stereotypes.

The reflection of the masculinity narrative reinforced during the period of USSR repression is still visible on women representation in Lithuania history nowadays. Representation of women is usually based on specific and more prominent individuals and does not provide much information on their lives and their footprint in the country's history. This is also noticeable in the context of women commemoration in public spaces of Vilnius city. Only 42 out of 2971 streets of the city have the names of honourable women or female historic figures and only 22 out of 377 commemorative plaques, sculptures and monuments are installed in memory of famous women.

Information on practises in disseminating gender balanced history in Vilnius is fragmented due to the large autonomy of Lithuanian municipal administrations and other entities in carrying out educational and/or cultural initiatives. Furthermore, there is no publicly available information on local strategies promoting visibility of women's footprint in history. Usually, initiatives to promote gender balanced history are pursued independently by the public institutions, as well as supported by private efforts. Recently there is a notable increase of exhibitions devoted to famous women, their work and input into the Lithuanian history. This was also noticed by the participants of Focus group and individual interviews with stakeholders.

Research participants shared the challenges faced in making the footprint of women more public and visible. This is mostly related to the lack of historiography, the stereotypical view of history as a male-dominated subject, the lack of methodological material and the invisibility of female figures in public urban spaces. A stereotypical approach to this issue also contributes to the challenges of attracting a diverse audience.

Participants of Focus group and individual interviews agreed that there is a need to find more innovative methods to engage youth to be more interested in history subject, as well as in women footprint in history. The fact that youth is not interested in the history was also confirmed during the Focus Group with schoolchildren. They shared that the education program of history subject, the methods applied, as well as the role of the teacher are important factors to increase interest in the history subject. Finally, interviewed youth agreed with the stakeholders about the methods that could help be applied to promote knowledge on women's footprint in history. Research participants indicated that the methods should be innovative and interactive, while information should reflect the experiences of youth and be provided through the lens of a young person.

